

Appendix to FastFlip: Compositional Error Injection Analysis

APPENDIX A PRUNING ERROR RANGE

Approxilyzer’s use of equivalence classes speeds up both FastFlip and the baseline analysis. However, the pilot is not a perfect predictor of the outcomes for the pruned injections (i.e., the rest of the equivalence class). Figure 5 in Approxilyzer [1] shows that some pruned injections have an outcome that significantly differs from that of the pilot. Therefore, Approxilyzer’s results cannot be considered to be the absolute ground truth for comparison.

We account for the potential discrepancy between the ground truth and Approxilyzer by calculating an error range around the achieved value of SDC protection. Using the results from Approxilyzer or FastFlip, we can determine, for each error site, 1) whether or not the outcome is SDC-Bad, and 2) whether the analysis actually injected an error at that site, or the outcome of an error at that site was inferred from the outcome of another error in the same equivalence class. Additionally, each error site can either be protected or unprotected, depending on whether the analysis selected the corresponding static instruction for protection. Using these factors, we divide all error sites into eight categories, and assign a variable to represent the number of error sites in each category:

Outcome:	Injected		Pruned	
	SDC-Bad	Other	SDC-Bad	Other
Protected	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>D</i>
Unprotected	<i>E</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>H</i>

Lastly, let R be the rate of outcome misprediction for pruned error sites for the benchmark. With this information, we can calculate the bounds on the actual value of protecting the selected instructions:

$$v_{\min} = \frac{A + (1 - R)C}{A + (1 - R)C + E + G + RH}$$

$$v_{\max} = \frac{A + C + RD}{A + C + RD + E + (1 - R)G}$$

Then, the value error range is the interval $[v_{\min}, v_{\max}]$. The value calculated in FastFlip’s approach always lies within this error range and is equal to:

$$v_{\text{calc}} = \frac{A + C}{A + C + E + G}$$

For FFT, LUD, and BScholes, we use the benchmark-specific pilot prediction inaccuracy from Figure 5 in Approxilyzer [1] (3%, 4%, and 10% respectively). For Campipe and SHA2, we consider the average inaccuracy from the same figure (4%).

APPENDIX B COMPARISON OF FASTFLIP AND APPROXILYZER WHEN SMALL SDCs ARE CONSIDERED ACCEPTABLE

Table I compares the utility of FastFlip and Approxilyzer when small SDCs (≤ 0.01) are considered acceptable (SDC-Good) and the analyses focus on protecting against errors that cause larger SDCs (SDC-Bad). Columns 1-2 show the benchmark name and version, respectively. Subsequent pairs of columns show the utility comparison for the target protection values 0.90, 0.95, and 0.99 (90%, 95%, and 99% of SDC-causing errors) respectively. The first column in each pair shows FastFlip’s achieved protection value. The second column shows the cost of protecting FastFlip’s selection, and compares this to the cost of protecting Approxilyzer’s selection. We exclude SHA2 for this evaluation as its applications require the calculated hashes to be fully precise.

FastFlip successfully meets all target values for all benchmarks. The maximum loss of value compared to the target is 0.014 (1.4%) for FFT-Large. In all cases, the target value is within FastFlip’s achieved value error range caused by injection pruning. For most benchmarks, the cost of protecting FastFlip’s selection of instructions is at most 0.020 (2%) more than the cost of protecting Approxilyzer’s selection. The exception is Campipe, for which FastFlip’s cost is higher by as much as 0.057 (5.7%) due to aggressive target adjustment.

The geomean cost of protecting FastFlip’s selection is 0.619, 0.720, and 0.849 for the target protection values 0.90, 0.95, and 0.99, respectively. FastFlip obtains the results in Table I at the same time as the results for the scenario where all SDCs are unacceptable for negligible additional analysis time (< 1 minute).

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Venkatagiri, A. Mahmoud, S. K. S. Hari, and S. V. Adve, “Approxilyzer: Towards a systematic framework for instruction-level approximate computing and its application to hardware resiliency,” in *MICRO*, 2016.

TABLE I: Comparison of FastFlip and Approxilyzer utility when SDCs with magnitude up to 0.01 are acceptable. A ✓ indicates that the achieved value is within the value error range of FastFlip.

Benchmark	Modif.	$v_{\text{trgt}} = 0.90$		$v_{\text{trgt}} = 0.95$		$v_{\text{trgt}} = 0.99$	
		Value	Cost (diff)	Value	Cost (diff)	Value	Cost (diff)
BScholes	None	0.900✓	0.645 (+0.013)	0.951✓	0.727 (+0.013)	0.990✓	0.821 (+0.000)
	Small	0.898✓	0.642 (+0.011)	0.949✓	0.724 (+0.013)	0.990✓	0.821 (+0.000)
	Large	0.892✓	0.681 (+0.012)	0.946✓	0.765 (+0.006)	0.990✓	0.849 (-0.012)
Campipe	None	0.900✓	0.576 (+0.031)	0.951✓	0.674 (+0.032)	0.991✓	0.802 (+0.030)
	Small	0.915✓	0.577 (+0.057)	0.958✓	0.674 (+0.054)	0.992✓	0.802 (+0.045)
	Large	0.903✓	0.694 (+0.024)	0.953✓	0.780 (+0.018)	0.992✓	0.895 (+0.016)
FFT	None	0.900✓	0.563 (+0.002)	0.950✓	0.687 (+0.004)	0.990✓	0.848 (+0.008)
	Small	0.904✓	0.579 (+0.012)	0.947✓	0.684 (-0.006)	0.989✓	0.845 (+0.002)
	Large	0.895✓	0.529 (-0.007)	0.936✓	0.625 (-0.028)	0.979✓	0.774 (-0.041)
LUD	None	0.900✓	0.657 (+0.004)	0.950✓	0.787 (+0.000)	0.990✓	0.932 (+0.002)
	Small	0.906✓	0.674 (+0.020)	0.950✓	0.787 (+0.000)	0.990✓	0.932 (+0.000)
	Large	0.903✓	0.638 (+0.009)	0.943✓	0.753 (-0.007)	0.989✓	0.884 (-0.002)